

МЕНСТРУАЛЬНА ФУНКЦІЯ У ЖІНОК З ДІАГНОСТОВАНОЮ ПАТОЛОГІЄЮ ЩИТОПОДІБНОЇ ЗАЛОБИ ПІСЛЯ COVID-19**Петрук А.О.**

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MENSTRUAL FUNCTION IN WOMEN WITH DIAGNOSED THYROID PATHOLOGY AFTER COVID-19**Petruk A.O.**

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Анотація

Мета. Вивчити особливості менструальної функції у жінок репродуктивного віку серед яких після перенесеного COVID-19 виявлено різні патології щитоподібної залози. Матеріали та методи. Було проведено дослідження за участю 60 жінок із порушенням менструальної функції та діагностованою патологією щитоподібної залози після інфікування COVID-19 протягом останнього року. Середній вік становив 27,1±0,7 року. Проведено загальноклінічне, лабораторне та гінекологічне обстеження, у тому числі УЗД щитоподібної залози, визначення рівня ТТГ, вільного Т4, вільного Т3, антитіл до ТПО, естрадіолу та прогестерону. Результати. Патологія щитоподібної залози виявлена у 43 жінок (71,7%): підгострий тиреоїдит у 16 (11,6%), автоімунний тиреоїдит у 38 (88,4%). Менструальна дисфункція серед цих пацієнток (n=43) включала опсоменорею (25,6%), вторинну аменорею (23,3%), метрорагію (16,3%), гіперменорею (11,6%), альгодисменорею (10%) та менорагію (14%). Гормональний профіль щитоподібної залози показав 23,3% з еутиреозом, 69,7% з субклінічним гіпотиреозом і 7% з субклінічним гіпертиреозом. При субклінічному гіпотиреозі (n=30) опсоменорея спостерігалася у 33,3%, вторинна аменорея — у 26,7%, метрорагія — у 13,3%, гіперменорея — у 6,7%, альгодисменорея — у 6,7% і менорагія — у 13,3%. Для еутиреоїдного статусу (n=10) опсоменорея була присутня у 10%, вторинна аменорея у 20%, метрорагія у 10%, гіперменорея у 30%, альгодисменорея у 10% та менорагія у 20%. Гіпертиреоз на фоні автоімунного тиреоїдиту виявлено у 3 жінок, метрорагія — у 2, альгодисменорея — у 1. Висновки. Порушення менструальної функції у жінок після перенесеного COVID-19 є наслідком патології щитоподібної залози, викликаной вірусом. Основними видами порушень менструального циклу є опсоменорея (25,6%), вторинна аменорея (23,3%), метрорагія (16,3%), гіперменорея (16,3%), альгоменорея (16,3%), менорагії (16,3%). Клінічний перебіг змінювався залежно від функції щитоподібної залози: субклінічний гіпотиреоз призвів до опсоменореї (33,3%) і вторинної аменореї (26,7%); еутиреоїдний стан призвів до гіперменореї (30%) та вторинної аменореї (20%); гіпертиреоз, викликаний метрорагіями. Раннє виявлення та лікування захворювань щитоподібної залози може покращити репродуктивне здоров'я жінки.

Abstract

The aim. To study the peculiarities of menstrual function in women of reproductive age, in whom various pathologies of the thyroid gland were detected after suffering from COVID-19. Materials and Methods. A study was conducted on 60 women with menstrual dysfunction and diagnosed thyroid pathology following COVID-19 infection within the last year. The average age was 27.1 ± 0.7 years. General clinical, laboratory, and gynecological examinations were performed, including thyroid ultrasound, and measurements of TSH, free T4, free T3, anti-TPO antibodies, estradiol, and progesterone levels. Results. Thyroid pathology was detected in 43 women (71.7%): subacute thyroiditis in 16 (11.6%), AIT in 38 (88.4%). Menstrual dysfunction in these patients ($n=43$) included opsomenorrhoea (25.6%), secondary amenorrhoea (23.3%), metrorrhagia (16.3%), hypermenorrhoea (11.6%), algodismenorrhoea (10%), and menorrhagia (14%). Hormonal thyroid profile showed 23.3% with euthyroidism, 69.7% with subclinical hypothyroidism, and 7% with subclinical hyperthyroidism. For subclinical hypothyroidism ($n=30$), opsomenorrhoea was present in 33.3%, secondary amenorrhoea in 26.7%, metrorrhagia in 13.3%, hypermenorrhoea in 6.7%, algodismenorrhoea in 6.7%, and menorrhagia in 13.3%. For euthyroid status ($n=10$), opsomenorrhoea was present in 10%, secondary amenorrhoea in 20%, metrorrhagia in 10%, hypermenorrhoea in 30%, algodismenorrhoea in 10%, and menorrhagia in 20%. Hyperthyroidism on the background of AIT was found in 3 women, with metrorrhagia in 2 and algodismenorrhoea in 1. Conclusions. Menstrual dysfunction in women after COVID-19 is a result of thyroid pathology caused by the virus. The main types of menstrual disorders are opsomenorrhoea (25.6%), secondary amenorrhoea (23.3%), metrorrhagia (16.3%), hypermenorrhoea (16.3%), algodismenorrhoea (16.3%), and menorrhagia (16.3%). The clinical course varied with thyroid function: subclinical hypothyroidism led to opsomenorrhoea (33.3%) and secondary amenorrhoea (26.7%); euthyroid state resulted in hypermenorrhoea (30%) and secondary amenorrhoea (20%); hyperthyroidism caused metrorrhagia. Early detection and treatment of thyroid disorders can improve women's reproductive health.

Ключові слова: захворюваність на COVID-19, менструальний цикл, репродуктивне здоров'я, ендокринна патологія, організація гінекологічної допомоги.

Keywords: COVID-19 incidence, menstrual cycle, reproductive health, endocrine pathology, organization of gynecological care.

It is widely known that the female reproductive system is one of the most sensitive and reactive systems to various external factors [1]. Therefore, it is logical that during the COVID-19 pandemic, under the viral load on the female body, the reproductive system is primarily affected: menstrual function is disrupted, fertility decreases, the incidence of gynecological pathology increases, and the risk of complicated pregnancies, spontaneous abortions, and stillbirths rises [2].

COVID-19 is a severe immunosuppressive disease that has a multifaceted impact on the entire body and can exacerbate pre-existing autoimmune (chronic) diseases. One of the most vulnerable organs remains the thyroid gland. The most common thyroid pathology is the emergence or exacerbation of autoimmune thyroiditis, which in turn can lead not only to structural changes in the thyroid tissue but also to various functional disorders of the gland [3, 4]. Due to the presence of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors in the thyroid gland, through which SARS-CoV-2 enters the cells, and the action of integrins, there is a high likelihood of developing thyrotoxicosis, subacute, and chronic thyroiditis following a COVID-19 infection [5, 6].

It should be noted that in the literature dedicated to the functional relationship between the thyroid gland and the female reproductive system, there is a lack of data on the correlation between changes in the ovaries and uterus against the background of COVID-19 and thyroid function, and vice versa. Additionally, we have not found scientific works that justify the principles of early diagnosis of menstrual dysfunctions developing against the background of viral thyroiditis.

THE AIM. To study the peculiarities of menstrual function in women of reproductive age who were diag-

nosed with various thyroid gland pathologies after suffering from COVID-19, in order to improve the quality of diagnosis and treatment of these disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. To achieve this goal, a study was conducted on 60 women with menstrual dysfunction and detected pathological changes in the thyroid gland after suffering from COVID-19 during the year. There were no pathological changes in the anamnesis of both the thyroid gland and the reproductive system in the patients who participated in the study.

The average age of patients included in the study was 27.1 ± 0.7 years.

The set of diagnostic studies included:

- general clinical, laboratory and gynecological examination,
- ultrasound of the thyroid gland,
- determination of pituitary hormones (TSH), thyroid gland (free T4 and free T3, AT-TPO) and sex hormones (estradiol and progesterone).

RESULTS. Analyzing the main features of the clinical characteristics of the patients, it should be noted that half of the women (50%) had a different number of pregnancies and deliveries in their anamnesis.

According to the results of the diagnosis of the thyroid gland, pathology was detected in 43 women (71.7%).

The structure of thyroid pathologies was distributed as follows: subacute thyroiditis – in 16 (11.6%), AIT – in 38 (88.4%).

In 17 women (39.5%) – pathology was detected using ultrasound signs; in 14 (32.5%) – it was detected by testing thyroid hormones, thyroid-stimulating hormone and antibodies to thyroid peroxidase in blood se-

rum; in 12 (27.9%) – only an uninformative and subjective palpation method was used to diagnose thyroid gland pathology.

According to ultrasound data, the increase in the thyroid gland in the examined women was accompanied by a homogeneous echo structure of the organ. The echogenicity of the gland tissue was normal in 11 patients (64.7%); slightly increased in 4 women (23.5%) and in 2 women (11.7%) diffuse hypoechoic areas without clear borders were detected.

During a comprehensive study of the features of menstrual dysfunction against the background of thyroid gland pathology, detected in female patients (n=43(100%)), we obtained the following data, which make it possible to determine the main types of menstrual dysfunction:

Fig. 1 Hormonal thyroid profile

Taking into account the obtained results, we decided to establish the interdependence between the violation of the menstrual cycle and the type of functional disorder of the thyroid gland. Thus, it was investigated that in the presence of subclinical hypothyroidism (n = 30 (100%)), the following clinical types of menstrual dysfunction were determined:

- 10 (33,3%) – opsomenorrhoea,
- 8 (26,7%) – secondary amenorrhoea,
- 4 (13,3%) – metrorrhagia,
- 2 (6,7%) – hypermenorrhoea,
- 2 (6,7%) – algodismenorrhoea,
- 4 (13,3%) – menorrhagia.

In the case of euthyroid status (n=10 (23.3%)), menstrual cycle disorders were as follows:

- 1 (10%) – opsomenorrhoea,
- 2 (20%) – secondary amenorrhoea,
- 1 (10%) – metrorrhagia,
- 3 (30%) – hypermenorrhoea,
- 1 (10%) – algodismenorrhoea,
- 2 (20%) – menorrhagia.

- 11 (25,6%) – opsomenorrhoea,
- 10 (23,3%) – secondary amenorrhoea,
- 7 (16,3%) – metrorrhagia,
- 5 (11,6%) – hypermenorrhoea,
- 4 (10%) – algodismenorrhoea,
- 6(14%) – menorrhagia.

In patients with thyroid pathology, the study of the hormonal thyroid profile (n=43 (71.7%)) revealed functional disorders. It turned out that among these patients, 23.3% had euthyroidism, 69.7% had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 7% had signs of subclinical hyperthyroidism.

With detected hyperthyroidism on the background of AIT, which was detected by us in only 3 examined, menstrual function was characterized by: metrorrhagia in 2 persons and aldodysmenorrhoea in 1 woman.

DISCUSSION. The results of our study confirm that COVID-19 significantly affects the function of the thyroid gland, which, in turn, leads to menstrual cycle disorders in women of childbearing age. The detected disorders are characteristic of patients with various forms of thyroid pathologies after suffering from COVID-19 and are mainly manifested in the form of opsomenorrhoea (25.6%) and secondary amenorrhoea (23.3%), which coincides with the results of numerous domestic and foreign studies. and indicate both a direct effect of transferred COVID-19 on the thyroid gland through ACE2 receptors, and an indirect one, through immune mechanisms, causing autoimmune processes and inflammatory reactions [4, 7, 8].

Taking into account the data obtained on the detection of thyroid pathology in 71.7% of women after

suffering from COVID-19, the importance of early diagnosis and monitoring of thyroid gland function in patients suffering from COVID-19 should be emphasized.

In view of the above, further research for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of the impact of COVID-19 on the thyroid gland and the reproductive system of a woman, which will allow the development of an effective treatment-diagnostic-prophylactic algorithm for these disorders. This will help not only in identifying and treating thyroid disorders, but also in reducing the frequency and severity of menstrual disorders, improving the overall reproductive health of women.

CONCLUSIONS. Disruption of menstrual function in women after suffering from COVID-19 is a consequence of thyroid gland pathology caused by the effect of the virus on the gland.

The main types of menstrual disorders in women after suffering from COVID-19: opsomenorrhoea (25.6%), secondary amenorrhoea (23.3%), metrorrhagia (16.3%), hypermenorrhoea (16.3%), algomenorrhoea (16, 3%), menorrhagia (16.3%).

The clinical course of menstrual cycle disorders in women after suffering from COVID-19 depended on the functional changes of the thyroid gland. Against the background of subclinical hypothyroidism, opsomenorrhoea (33.3%) and secondary amenorrhoea (26.7%) prevailed in patients; on the background of euthyroid state – hypermenorrhoea (30%) and secondary amenorrhoea (20%); with hyperthyroidism - metrorrhagia.

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